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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF
IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLETS CONTAINING
FEBUXOSTAT**Narottam Pal^{1*}, A.Srinivasa Rao², Farah Naheen Sultana³, Devakoti Nikitha³²Professor & Principal, Bhaskar Pharmacy College, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Ranga Reddy Dist, Hyderabad-500075.³ResearchSchloars, Bhaskar Pharmacy College, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Ranga Reddy Dist, Hyderabad-500075.**Abstract:**

The aim of the present study is to develop and evaluate the immediate release tablet of Febuxostat by direct compression method. The Superdisintegrant Primojel, Ac-Di-Sol and PolyplasdoneXL10 were used for immediate release of drug from tablet. The prepared tablets were evaluated for all pre-compression parameters and post-compression parameters. The drug excipients interaction was investigated by FTIR. All formulation showed compliances with Pharmacopoeial standards. The study reveals that formulations prepared by direct compression F3 exhibit highest dissolution using Crospovidone showed faster drug release 98.01% over the period of 45min while disintegration time of the tablet was showed 25sec comparison to other formulations of Febuxostat.

Keywords: Febuxostat, superdisintegrant and Immediate release tablet.

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INTRODUCTION:

The Oral route is one of the most sought after route for the systemic effect due to its ease of ingestion, simple, safest, convenient, non-invasive, versatility and most importantly, patient compliance. Solid oral delivery systems are cheaply manufactured because they don't require sterile conditions ¹. Although, increased focus and interest generated in the area of controlled release and targeted drug delivery system in recent years, tablet dosage forms that are intended to be swallowed whole, disintegrate, and release their medicaments fast and furiously in the gastrointestinal tract ². An ideal dosage regimen of drug therapy is the one, which immediately nab the desired therapeutic concentration of drug in plasma (or at the site of action) and maintains it constantly for the entire duration treatment ³. Of late, the scientists have focused their attention on the formulation immediately released tablet. The effort of developing a rapidly disintegrating tablet is accomplished by using suitable diluents and super disintegrants ⁴

Definition: Immediate Release Tablets: Immediate release tablets are invented to disintegrate and release their dosage form with no special rate controlling features, such as special coatings and other techniques. Immediate release tablets are those which disintegrate swiftly and get dissolved to release the medicaments.⁵

The oral bioavailability of drug dependent on disintegration, dissolution and various physiological factors.⁶ An immediate release dosage form helps amanufacturer to diversify market and simultaneously offering patients a convenient dosage form or dosage regimen. ⁷ The development of enhanced oral protein delivery technology by immediate release tablets which may release the drugs at an enhanced rate are very promising for the delivery of poorly soluble drugs high molecular weight protein and peptide.

The oral route remains the perfect route for the administration of therapeutic agents because the low cost of therapy, manufacturing and ease of administration lead to high levels of patient compliance, ⁸. Many patients require quick onset of action in particular therapeutic condition and consequently immediate release of medicament is required. It is estimated that 50% of the population is affected by this problem, which results in a high incidence of ineffective therapy.

Figure 1.1 Essential Requirements For Immediate Release Tablets

Advantages of Immediate Release Drug Delivery System:

- Improved compliance / added convenience, solubility, stability, bioavailability.
- Allows high drug loading, cost-effective.
- Ability to provide advantages of liquid medication in the form of solid preparation.
- Adaptable and amenable to existing processing and packaging machinery.
- Decreased dissolution and disintegration times for immediate release oral dosage forms.⁹

Disadvantage:

- Frequent dosing is necessary for a drug with a short half-life.
- Drug release at a time may produce high plasma concentration which may produce toxicity.
- Patient may suffer from tremors therefore they have difficulty to take tablet, powder and liquids. In dysphasia physical obstacles and adherence to an oesophagus may cause gastrointestinal ulceration.
- Swallowing of solid dosage forms like tablet and capsules and produce difficulty for young adult of incomplete development of muscular and nervous system and elderly patients suffer from dysphasia.

CRITERIA FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Immediate release dosage form shouldIn the case of solid dosage it should dissolve or disintegrate in the stomach within a short period.

- In the case of liquid dosage form it should be compatible with taste masking.
- Be portable without fragility concern.
- Have a pleasing mouth feel.

- It should not leave minimal or no residue in the mouth after oral administration.
- Exhibit low sensitivity to environmental condition as humidity and temperature.
- Be manufactured using conventional processing and packaging equipment at low cost.
- Rapid dissolution and absorption of drug, which may produce rapid onset of action.¹⁰

Conventional Techniques Used for Preparation of Immediate Release Tablets:

Several technologies are available to manufacture immediate-release tablets. The most common preparation methods are molding, lyophilization or freeze drying, direct compression, spray drying and sublimation.¹¹

Figure 1.2 : Types Of Conventional Techniques Of Immediate Release Tablet

Tablet Molding Technique: In this technology, water-soluble ingredients are incorporated to disintegrate and dissolve the tablet more swiftly. The hydroalcoholic solvents are used to moistened powder blend and then apply compression pressure that is lower than the conventional tablets compression to mold the tablet. The solvent is then

Figure 1.4 Advantages Of Wet Granulation Method

removed by air-drying. Dissolution is enhanced by a porous structure of molded tablets.¹¹

Direct Compression: In which tablets formulations are directly compressed from a powder blend of suitable excipients and API is called a direct compression method. Pre-treatment of blended powder by dry or wet granulation procedure is not necessary. Its provide merits mostly in terms of speedy production, as it requires less machinery, reduced number of personnel, fewer unit operations and significantly less processing time along with improved product stability.¹²

Granulation Technique: It is a process of size enlargement in which small particles convert into larger agglomerates and make it physically stronger. It is beneficial to avoid segregation of the product's constituent, refine powder flow and handling and minimize the dustiness.

Figure 1.3 Types Of Granulation Techniques

It is ideally spherical, the smaller particle size is efficiently filling the void spaces between granules. This method can also be classified as two types.¹³

(A) Wet Granulation:

Wet granulation process make easy fine particles run into severity-feed drug manufacturing. Usually, immediate release formulation is granulated with addition into fine particles accumulation an aqueous solution of a binding polymer. Controlled release formulation.¹⁴

Direct Compression	Wet Granulation	Dry Granulation
Blending	Blending	Blending
-	Wet massing and screening	Slugging/roller compression
-	Drying	-
-	Dry screening	Screening
Blending (with lubrication)	Blending (with lubrication)	Blending (with lubrication)
Compaction	Compaction	Compaction

Table 1.1 Steps Involved In This Process Of Preparation Of Tablets By Conventional Technique

Mass-Extrusion: In this technology softening the blend of active drug with water-soluble solvent methanol, polyethylene glycol and softened mass put into the extruder to form a cylinder shape of the product and segmented with using the heated blade to formulate a dosage form as tablets .15

Solid Dispersions:

Solid products containing at least two different components, mainly hydrophilic matrix and a hydrophobic drug. The matrix can be either crystalline or amorphous. This method deal with the challenge of mixing a matrix and drug, preferably on a molecular level, while matrix and drug are generally poorly miscible 19. When formulating immediate release solid dosage forms from solid amorphous dispersion for oral administration to effective use in an environment such as the GI tract of a human, it is often desirable to increase the amount of dispersion occurs in the dosage form.16

(B) Dry Granulation: In dry granulation process the powder mixture is compressed without the use of heat and solvent. The two basic procedures are to form a compact of material by compression and then to mill the compact to obtain granules. Below two methods are used for dry granulation .17

Lyophilization: It depends on simple principle i.e. sublimation. The sublimation is processed in which conversion of a substance from a solid state to vapor state, without changing in the liquid phase. Lyophilisation is performed at temperature and pressure conditions below the triple point. The whole process is performed at low temperature and pressure by applying vacuum; hence it is suitable for drying of thermolabile compounds. 18

Novel Granulation Technologies:

- (a) **Pneumatic Dry Granulation (PDG):** It is a novel technique of dry method in which the formulation of granules is carried out by automatically or semi-automatically. This techniques granule has excellent properties as compared to dry granulation, direct compression, wet granulation and granules are showing high compressibility and flowability The outcome can be attained without utilizing exotic and high-cost excipients. 19
- (b)
- (c) **Freeze Granulation Technology (FGT):** Integrated Biosystems, Inc. (California, USA) had patented freeze GT that results in spherical and free flowing granules with ideal homogeneity. Its require spraying of a suspension containing powder into liquid nitrogen where the drops were swiftly frozen to form granules which upon subsequent freeze-drying yields dry granules. 20
- (d)
- (e) **Spray Drying Granulation:** This technology facilitated to improved flow, homogeneous distribution of colors, drug and required less lubricant as compared to wet massed products. It can be co-precipitate an active pharmaceutical ingredient with a suitable polymer to form a stable amorphous solid dispersion and promote improved bioavailability and dissolution rate of many drug products.21
- (f)
- (g) **TOPO (TOPO Granulator) Technology:** Hermes Pharma has developed a unique technology

Figure 1.5 : Stages Of Madg Technique

(h) **Continuous Flow Technology:** This method does not use liquid to precede chain reaction.

Figure 1.6 Advantages Of Continuous Flow Technology

Granules are formulated in the inclined drum in which powder is loaded to inlet duct and formulated granules are removed from the other side. Every day up to 12 tons of granules can produce by CF technology ²².

(i) **Thermal Adhesion Granulation Process:**

It is an alternate to moist granulation and requires a small quantity of binder liquid and heat to produce agglomeration. Moreover, the granulation process is facilitating by the use of heat. The mixture of

excipient and API is heated at 30-130 °C temperature in a closed chamber that is set for tumble rotation to produce the agglomeration process of the powder particle. This technique terminates the drying process because less amount of liquid is used and that is consumed during agglomeration of powder particles. After cooling and sieving required particle size of granules can be obtained .²³

(j) Granurex Technology:

This technology consistently and precisely accomplishes the powder layering processes, single coating, and multiple coating processes and powder layers that manifest the accuracy and better drug release mechanism. ²⁴

(k) Foamed Binder Technologies:

It assists in achieving an improved wet granulation product, by using with methocel polymers and homogenous distribution of binder solution to drug mixture. It decreases the need for water and provides reproducibility.²⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Febuxostat-Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, Primojel-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Ac-Di-Sol-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Polyplasdone XL10-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Beta-Cyclodextrin-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, MCC-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Aspartame-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mg stearate-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Talc-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd.

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODE								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Febuxostat	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Primojel	40	80	120	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ac-Di-Sol	-	-	-	40	80	120	-	-	-
PolyplasdoneXL10	-	-	-	-	-	-	40	80	120
Beta-Cyclodextrin	10	20	30	10	20	30	10	20	30
MCC	122	72	22	122	72	22	122	72	22
Aspartame	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Mg stearate	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Talc	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Total Weight of Tablet (mg)	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

METHODOLOGY

Characterization of Febuxostat

Organoleptic properties:

Take a small quantity of sample and spread it on the white paper and examine it visually for color, odour and texture.

Determination of Febuxostat Melting point

The melting point of Febuxostat was determined by capillary tube method according to the USP. A sufficient quantity of Febuxostat powder was introduced into the capillary tube to give a compact column of 4-6 mm in height. The tube was introduced in electrical melting point apparatus and the temperature was raised. The melting point was recorded, which is the temperature at which the last solid particle of Febuxostat in the tube passed into liquid phase.

Buffer Preparation:

Preparation of 0.2M Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate solution: Accurately weighed 27.218 gm of monobasic potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 1000mL of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of 0.2M sodium hydroxide solution:

Accurately weighed 8 gm sodium hydroxide pellets were dissolved 1000ml of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer:

Accurately measured 250ml of 0.2M potassiumDihydrogen ortho phosphate and 112.5 ml 0.2M NaOH was taken into the 1000ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to 1000ml with distilled water.

Analytical method development for Febuxostat:

a) Determination of absorption maxima

A spectrum of the working standards was obtained by scanning from 200-400nm against the reagent blank to fix absorption maxima. The λ_{max} was found to be 315nm. Hence all further investigation was carried out at the same wavelength.

b) Preparation of Standard graph in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Total weight of tablets = 300 mg

100 mg of Febuxostat was dissolved in 100ml of Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8., form primary stock

10ml was transferred to another volumetric flask made up to 100ml with Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8, from this secondary stock was taken separately and made up to 10 ml with Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8, to produce 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 μ g/ml respectively. The absorbance was measured at 315nm by using a UV spectrophotometer.

Formulation Development:

Drug and different concentrations for super Disintegrates and required ingredients were

accurately weighed and passed through a 40-mesh screen to get uniform size particles and mixed in a glass mortar for 15 minutes. The obtained blend was lubricated with Magnesium stearate and glidant (Talc) was added and mixing was continued for further 5 minutes. The resultant mixture was directly compressed into tablets by using punch of rotary tablet compression machine.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

Organoleptic properties

Table: Organoleptic properties

S NO.	Properties	Reported results	Observed results
1	State	Solid	Solid
2	Colour	White	White
3	Odour	Odourless	Odourless
4	Melting point	129.2-129.8	129.5

Calibration curve of Febuxostat:

The standard curve of Febuxostat was obtained and good correlation was obtained with R² value of 0.999, the medium selected was pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Table: Standard graph values of Febuxostat at 315 nm in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Concentrations (μ g/ml)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.119
4	0.238
6	0.347
8	0.461
10	0.574

Fig : Standard curve of Febuxostat

Evaluation:**Characterization of Precompression blends:**

The Precompression blend of Febuxostat was characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. Angle of repose was less than 35.23°, Carr's index values were less than 20.01 for the Precompression blend of all the batches indicating good to fair flowability and compressibility. Hausner's ratio was less than 1.26 for all batches indicating good flow properties.

Table: Physical properties of Precompression blend

Formulation code	Angle of repose (°)	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	35.13±0.032	0.4236±0.0026	0.4854±0.0018	12.73±0.0494	1.14±0.0014
F2	35.15±0.041	0.4230±0.0020	0.4766±0.0033	11.23±0.1272	1.12±0.0035
F3	29.24±0.008	0.4127±0.0180	0.4821±0.0029	14.36±0.7566	1.16±0.0000
F4	27.47±0.027	0.4227±0.0038	0.5231±0.0253	19.19±0.0565	1.23±0.0071
F5	35.12±0.019	0.3823±0.0032	0.4852±0.0044	20.01±0.0848	1.26±0.0000
F6	34.99±0.003	0.3910±0.0014	0.4650±0.0036	15.90±0.3040	1.16±0.0070
F7	33.86±0.002	0.2896±0.0014	0.3449±0.0013	16.04±0.3676	1.18±0.0424
F8	35.23±0.001	0.3100±0.0035	0.3655±0.0031	15.19±0.2969	1.17±0.0070
F9	32.61±0.001	0.3925±0.0026	0.4614±0.0028	14.93±0.9545	1.16±0.0070

All the values represent n=3

Evaluation of tablets:**Physical evaluation of Febuxostat immediate release tablets:**

The results of the weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability and drug content of tablets are given in table 8.3. All the tablets of different batches complied with the official requirement of weight variation as their weight variation passes the limit. The hardness of the tablets ranged from 4.0 – 4.9 kg/cm² and the friability values were < 0.61 % indicating that the tablets were compact and hard. The thickness of the tablets ranged from 3.15- 3.95 mm. All the formulations satisfied the content of the drug as they contained 96.28-99.35 % of Febuxostat and good uniformity in drug content was observed. Thus all physical attributes of the prepared tablets were found to be practically within control limits.

Table : Physical evaluation of Febuxostat

Formulation code	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (cm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Content Uniformity (%)	Disintegration Time (Sec)
F1	296.21	3.69	4.2	0.36	98.16	43
F2	298.80	3.48	4.9	0.24	97.62	36
F3	295.16	3.15	4.6	0.59	99.35	25
F4	299.60	3.75	4.1	0.37	96.28	51
F5	296.21	3.61	4.7	0.49	97.19	46
F6	298.52	3.95	4.3	0.36	99.25	40
F7	296.79	3.47	4.2	0.61	99.61	45
F8	298.31	3.64	4.0	0.48	98.18	38
F9	297.10	3.18	4.8	0.57	97.29	31

Figure : Disintegration Test (Sec)

In vitro release studies:The drug release rate from tablets was studied using the USP type II dissolution test apparatus. The dissolution medium was 900 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 75 rpm at a temperature of $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Samples of 5 ml were collected at different time intervals up to 1 hr and has analyzed after appropriate dilution by using UV spectrophotometer at 315 nm.

Table :In vitro dissolution data for formulation F1-F9

TIME (MIN)	% OF DRUG RELEASE								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	14.37	17.33	40.18	10.27	16.18	19.13	12.36	16.34	20.35
10	25.39	29.57	55.68	22.95	29.32	35.95	25.48	29.47	37.22
15	38.37	42.36	62.15	35.89	37.25	48.66	38.99	41.23	49.63
20	47.69	58.75	75.78	46.77	50.87	64.29	46.62	59.65	55.77
25	54.76	66.33	83.84	54.83	65.83	73.85	59.75	65.74	71.32
30	69.54	78.18	97.62	62.16	71.45	81.58	72.31	73.18	83.17
45	83.58	89.65	98.01	71.28	86.73	92.56	81.36	85.62	95.48

From the table it was evident that the formulation prepared with Primojel were showed good drug release i.e., F3 formulation (97.01%) in higher concentration of blend i.e. 120 mg. Formulations prepared with Ac-Di-Sol showed good drug release i.e., 92.56% (F6 formulation) in 120 mg concentration. When increase in the concentration of Primojel drug release increased. Formulations prepared with PolyplasdoneXL10 showed maximum drug release i.e., 95.48% (F9 formulation) at 45 min in 120 mg of blend.

Among all formulations F3 considered as optimized formulation which showed maximum drug release at 45 min i.e., 98.01%. Primojel showed good release when compared to Ac-Di-Sol and PolyplasdoneXL10. Finally concluded that F3 formulation contains Primojel was optimized formulation.

The formulations prepared with Beta-Cyclodextrin to increase the solubility, When the Concentration of Beta-Cyclodextrin was increased drug release also increased. The present work involves the formulation development, optimization and *in-vitro* evaluation of immediate release tablets by direct compression technique. Since Febuxostat is BCS Class-II drug, direct compression technique was opted to increase its solubility and dissolution rate.

Table : Release Kinetics:

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
40.18	5	2.236	1.604	0.699	1.777	8.036	0.0249	-0.396	59.82	4.642	3.911	0.731
55.68	10	3.162	1.746	1.000	1.647	5.568	0.0180	-0.254	44.32	4.642	3.539	1.103
62.15	15	3.873	1.793	1.176	1.578	4.143	0.0161	-0.207	37.85	4.642	3.358	1.284
75.78	20	4.472	1.880	1.301	1.384	3.789	0.0132	-0.120	24.22	4.642	2.893	1.748
83.84	25	5.000	1.923	1.398	1.208	3.354	0.0119	-0.077	16.16	4.642	2.528	2.113
97.62	30	5.477	1.990	1.477	0.377	3.254	0.0102	-0.010	2.38	4.642	1.335	3.306
98.01	45	6.708	1.991	1.653	0.299	2.178	0.0102	-0.009	1.99	4.642	1.258	3.384

Figure :Zero order release kinetics graph

Figure: Higuchi release kinetics graph

Figure :Peppas release kinetics graph

Figure :First order release kinetics graph

Optimised formulation F3 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation F3 was followed Higuchi release kinetics mechanism.

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies by FTIR studies:

Febuxostat was mixed with various proportions of excipients showed no colour change at the end of two months, providing no drug-Excipient interactions.

Fig : FTIR spectra of pure drug

Fig :FTIR spectra of optimized formulation

From the above studies it was found that there was no shifting in the major peaks which indicated that there were no significant interactions occurred between the Febuxostat and excipients used in the preparation of different Febuxostat Immediate Release formulations. Therefore the drug and excipients are compatible to form stable.

Formulations under study, The FTIR spectra of Febuxostat and physical mixture used for optimized formulation were obtained and these are depicted in above figures. From the FTIR data it was evident that the drug and excipients does not have any interactions. Hence they were compatible.

Table: Peaks characterization for pure Febuxostat

Functional group	Reference wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Obtained wave number (cm ⁻¹)
C=O (carbonyl)	1656-1715	1658.51
-C=C-Aromatic	1450-1650	1406.00-1598.67
Amide	3675.36	3646.83

Table: Peaks characterization for Optimized formulation Febuxostat

Functional group	Reference wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Obtained wave number (cm ⁻¹)
C=O (carbonyl)	1656-1715	1658.14-1742.11
-C=C-Aromatic	1450-1650	1406-02-1598.22
Amide	3675.36	3644.05

CONCLUSION:

Preformulation studies of Febuxostat were performed; the FT-IR analysis revealed that the Superdisintegrants and excipients used were compatible with Febuxostat. Immediate release tablets of Febuxostat are to be prepared by direct compression technique using Superdisintegrants, namely Primojel, Ac-Di-Sol and PolyplasdoneXL10. Amongst all the formulations, formulation containing Primojel as superdisintegrants is fulfilling all the parameters satisfactorily. It has shown excellent *in vitro* disintegration compared to other Superdisintegrants. Combines multiple mechanisms to achieve disintegration at low levels without forming gel i.e. require slow dissolution, disintegration and provides rapid disintegration in direct compression tablet as well increases tablet breaking force and reduces friability; enhances the dissolution of poorly soluble drugs. Apart from all the formulations, F3 formulation showed maximum drug release (97.01%) at the end of 45 min.

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